

K2 Observations of Galactic RRd Stars

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Abstract

We have analysed high-precision photometry of 77 double-mode RR Lyrae (RRd) stars observed by NASA’s *Kepler-K2* mission during Campaigns 1-18. Among those stars, we have identified several low-period ratio variables, belonging either to a subclass of “anomalous” RRd stars (Soszyński *et al.*, 2016) or to a separate shorter-period subclass recently identified by Prudil *et al.* (2017). A non-radial mode with the period ratio of $P_x/P_1 \sim 0.615$ has been detected in most RRd stars of our sample. In majority of these variables, at least one subharmonic of the non-radial frequency is also present. Our findings indicate that excitation of the non-radial mode is a common property of the RRd stars. The same non-radial pulsation is also commonly detected in the RRc stars. We show that properties of this puzzling mode are essentially the same in both groups of RR Lyrae-type pulsators.

1 Introduction

RRd stars are a subclass of the RR Lyrae variables, in which two radial modes, the fundamental and the first overtone, are simultaneously excited. Such variables are rare and not a single one has been found the original *Kepler* field (Nemeč *et al.*, 2013). Only with the *Kepler-K2* mission a high precision space photometry has finally been collected for a large sample of RRd stars. We are now in position to study their pulsation in great detail.

In this report we discuss 77 RRd variables observed during *K2* Campaigns 1-18. For most of these objects we have derived accurate photometry either with the EAP pipeline (Plachy *et al.*, 2018) or with the PyKE pipeline (Still & Barclay, 2012). For the remaining ones, we have used the standard *Kepler* PDCSap photometry provided by the *K2* archive. The latter is generally of somewhat lower quality. For all the stars we have performed detailed frequency analysis, using a standard Fourier Transform, followed by a consecutive frequency prewhitening. We note that four stars of our sample have already been studied before by other authors (Molnár *et al.*, 2015; Kurtz *et al.*, 2016; Plachy *et al.*, 2017).

A paper presenting full results of our analysis is being readied for publication (Nemeč *et al.*, 2019).

2 RRd variables in K2 fields

In Fig. 1 we present the Petersen diagram (the period ratio vs. period diagram) for the *K2* RRd stars (plotted with red asterisks). For comparison, we also display the “classical” RRd stars of the Galactic bulge (Soszyński *et al.*, 2014), the anomalous RRd stars collected from several stellar systems (Smolec *et al.*, 2015; Jurcsik *et al.*, 2015; Soszyński *et al.*, 2016; Smolec *et al.*, 2017a) and the so-called “Prudil’s stars” (Prudil *et al.*, 2017).¹

Most of the RRd variables of the *K2* sample are typical double-mode RR Lyrae pulsators and fall on a tight progres-

Figure 1: Petersen diagram for radial modes of RRd stars. The *K2* RRd stars are plotted with red asterisks. “Classical” RRd stars, anomalous RRd stars and “Prudil’s stars” are displayed with black dots, open blue circles and blue triangles, respectively.

sion defined by the classical RRd stars. There are several objects, though (marked with large red symbols), which behave differently. Three *K2* variables are placed firmly among anomalous RRd pulsators. In two of them pulsation modes are modulated (Smolec *et al.*, 2015; Plachy *et al.*, 2017). This is a very frequent phenomenon in anomalous RRd stars, but is not observed in the classical RRd pulsators. Four other *K2* variables with low period ratios and short periods belong to a subclass of the “Prudil’s stars”. In all seven exceptional objects, pulsations are strongly dominated by the radial fundamental mode $A_0/A_1 = 1.4 - 7.6$, which is another difference between them and the classical RRd pulsators.

¹For full discussion of different subclasses of the RRd pulsators the reader is referred to Smolec *et al.* (2017b).

Figure 2: Fourier frequency spectra of 3 RRd stars, after prewhitening the data of all the signal related to the radial modes. Red vertical dashed lines mark frequencies of the removed radial modes.

3 Secondary modes

For all RRd stars of our sample we have conducted a search for secondary low-amplitude pulsations. After prewhitening the data of the two radial modes, their harmonics and their combination frequencies, we have detected in many *K2* RRd variables an additional variability with frequency, f_x . Linear combinations of f_x with frequencies of the radial modes are also usually present. The period ratio of this secondary mode to the first radial overtone, P_x/P_1 , **is always close to 0.615** and its amplitude is always very low and rarely exceeds 10mmag. **This is the same period ratio which is commonly observed in the first overtone RR Lyrae (RRc) stars** (Moskalik *et al.*, 2015; Netzel *et al.*, 2015b). This period ratio cannot be explained with any two radial modes, implying that frequency f_x **must be associated with a nonradial mode of pulsation**. In many RRd stars a significant signal has also been found at $\sim 0.5f_x$ or $\sim 1.5f_x$, or both. These subharmonics always appear together with the parent mode, f_x , and never alone. The presence of the subharmonic (half-integer) frequencies is another similarity to the RRc variables. Interestingly, the f_x mode has been detected only in the classical RRd variables. It has not been detected in any of the "Prudil's stars" or the anomalous RRd stars.

In Fig. 2 we display Fourier frequency spectra for 3 classical RRd stars. The spectra are computed after prewhitening the data of all the signal related to the radial modes. The frequency axis is normalized by the frequency of the first radial overtone, f_1 . Such a normalization is adopted to better show how similar the frequency patterns in different RRd stars are. In all 3 variables of Fig. 2 the f_x mode is unambiguously detected. Its subharmonics are also clearly seen, although only in two variables both subharmonics are present. The Fourier peak at f_x is sometimes visibly broadened or split, indicating that the mode is not stationary. A detailed time-dependent analysis reveals that both the amplitude and the phase of f_x

mode are strongly variable. This is in contrast to the properties of the radial modes, which are usually almost perfectly stable.

It is interesting to establish how often the f_x mode is excited in the RRd stars. Because this mode is always very weak, we have to use the best data available to get this estimate. Therefore, we limit our sample to only those stars for which EAP or PyKE photometry is available. Furthermore, we limit the sample to the classical RRd stars, the only subclass in which f_x mode is detected. Such restricted subsample consists of 57 variables. Among those objects, the f_x mode is clearly detected in 43 RRd variables, which is 75% of the sample. Subharmonics of f_x have lower amplitude and are even more difficult to detect. Yet, they are found in 34 RRd variables. This constitutes 60% of the RRd sample and 79% of the stars in which f_x is present.

We can restrict the sample even further by accepting only stars with EAP photometry. The EAP data are somewhat better than PyKE data, especially when the field is crowded. The new subsample is limited to only 40 RRd stars, but this is the highest quality subsample we can select. The incidence rate of detecting the f_x frequency increases now to 85% (34 stars) and of detecting its subharmonic to 68% (27 stars). Clearly, the better the data the higher the probability of finding the f_x mode. This indicates that we have probably not yet reached the true incidence rates and the numbers given above should be treated only as lower limits. We conclude that **excitation of the f_x mode and its subharmonics is very common in the RRd stars**. The mode appears in the majority and possibly in all of the classical RRd stars. In most cases, the mode is accompanied by at least one subharmonic.

Figure 3: Petersen diagram for secondary modes of RRc and RRd stars. Period ratios are plotted vs. first overtone period, P_1 . The RRc stars of the Galactic Bulge (Netzel *et al.*, 2015a,b) are displayed with black dots. The RRd variables of the K2 sample are plotted with red asterisks.

4 Similarity of RRc and RRd stars

Secondary modes with period ratio of $P_x/P_1 = 0.60 - 0.64$ have been detected in nearly 300 RRc variables (Smolec *et al.*, 2017b). On the Petersen diagram the RRc stars form three well-separated horizontal sequences, which are centered on $P_x/P_1 = 0.613$, 0.632 and 0.631 (Fig. 3). The RRd stars of our sample fit into this pattern very nicely. Vast majority of them are placed on the lowest of the three sequences. This is to be expected, because the lowest sequence is the most populated among the three. The properties of the f_x mode are also the same in both groups of variables. In both RRc and RRd stars, the f_x modes:

- have similar period ratio with the first radial overtone;
- are usually accompanied by subharmonics (half-integer frequencies) at $\sim 0.5f_x$ and/or at $\sim 1.5f_x$.
- are detected in almost every star for which high precision space photometry is available (see Moskalik *et al.* (2015) for discussion of the incidence rate in RRc stars).
- have amplitudes in the same range;
- are nonstationary, while dominant radial modes are usually almost perfectly stable;

The similarity of the f_x mode in the RRd and the RRc variables is really striking. Clearly, in both subgroups of RR Lyrae pulsators we observe the same phenomenon. Consequently, **for both RRd and RRc stars a common explanation has to be found for f_x** . Because of the observed period ratio, this signal cannot be identified with any radial mode. Thus, **the f_x frequency must be associated with a nonradial mode of pulsation**. A promising interpretation has recently been put forward by Dziembowski (2016). In the proposed scenario, the f_x frequency corresponds to the first harmonic of the excited mode of $\ell = 8$ or $\ell = 9$.

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